

SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES COMMUNICATE USING HETEROGENEOUS SCHEMA

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ABSTRACT

During the past decade usage of online social network sites (SSN) has grown dramatically and rapidly, with the starting of some social sites like Facebook, Twitter, Orkut etc. The Facebook itself now boasts more than 400 million users in the world. We propose a Peer-to-Peer architecture namely P2P-iSN to integrate and collect the heterogeneous SNSs. The P2P-iSN allows different users from heterogeneous SNSs to communicate without evolving the SNSs they have registered with. So in our proposed system by identifying "Global relationship Model" (GRM) among registered users over heterogeneous SNSs. This system allows for users from different SNSs to interconnect their various networks. Integrated heterogeneous SNSs provide different services of different SNSs over a single platform.

KEYWORD: SSN, GRM, Facebook, Twitter, Peer-to-Peer

INTRODUCTION

Today's social networking sites (SNS) have become an essential part of our day-to-day life. We share a lot of data on these sites. There are many SNSs available today and many more are being added every day. So users use many more SNSs to share data with friends, family, and business. This communication medium gave rise to a complex structure whether a user really likes the SNS which he uses more or he needs another SNS other than he uses more. So for getting better performance users can get registered with multiple social networking sites for different social network applications. Users use multiple SNS accounts, share and display all information to each and every site. The content of the same user on various social networking sites may overlap. So it is difficult for users to manage content across different SNSs.

To overcome this problem, we integrate all the social networking sites (SNS) a user uses together and help the user understand & share the data and friend list and many other things. So as the user is efficient to access the system easily. As the complexity of SNSs increases, some researchers have been working on many methods to connect the user and aggregate data across SNSs. By using a single ID, SNSs allow users to leverage the information and publish their data on multiple SNSs. In this article, we first propose a peer-to-peer (P2P) network, namely P2P-iSN, to integrate heterogeneous SNSs and establish global relationships over the integrated SNSs.

LITERATURE SURVEY

I. Study of Existing system

- Homogeneous system users only communicate with each other.
Eg. Facebook users only communicate with Facebook users
- No heterogeneous users communicate with each other.
- Messages are not sent when users are offline

II. Traditional system:-

The traditional system lacks the integration of SNSs and thus makes the use of integrated SNSs quite difficult.

III. Limitations of the traditional method:

There are many limitations to the existing system :-

- The traditional system is a single SNS system.
- It lacks the peer to handle the SNS.
- It cannot understand the relationship between different SNSs.
- It cannot effectively use offline and online SNS data together.
- It cannot share data with various SNSs.

- It cannot integrate the peer with desktop and Phone together.
- It cannot maintain the data that is common offline which can be used for analysis of the data.
- It does have widgets to monitor the SNS.

For completing our research we study some research paper.

- 1) Light Flood: Minimizing Redundant Messages and Maximizing the Scope of Peer-to-Peer Search
By Song Jiang, Member, IEEE, Lei Guo, Member, IEEE, Xiaodong Zhang, Senior Member, IEEE, and Haodong Wang.
- 2) Integration of Heterogeneous Social Networks
- 3) Incentive Mechanisms for Peer-to-Peer Systems
By Bin Yu and Munindar P. Singh
- 4) Online Social Network Sites and the Concept of Social Capital

CONCLUSION

All the survey paper and IEEE paper states how the existing system work and how our system work on the basis of these survey paper. this survey paper states that how the two system are connected with each other by heterogeneous system

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